

Performance of Basic Education in Kenya: Strategic Challenges, Choices and Options

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 16 February 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Basic Education in Kenya School performance in Kenya Strategic choices for learning Strategic options for schools</p>	<p>This study looked at the existing strategic challenges affecting the basic education in Kenya. Specifically, the study highlighted the challenges related to system culture, operationalization of strategic management, participative decision-making, shared government vision, external circumstances and internal organizational school system that affect the performance of basic education in Kenya. The study further proposed possible strategic options (Balanced Score Card, McKinsey's Strategic Horizons, PESTEL Strategic) that can be used to address the strategic challenges and how they can be applied.</p>

1. Introduction

Education is the weapon of human development. For this reason, the development of the skills and knowledge of the people of a nation through the education process constitutes one of the prerequisites of national development. Basic Education is a major foundation for social, economic and political development of a nation (UNESCO, 2005). Provision of educational opportunities, especially of basic education has been an objective of investment of many countries all over the world. Basic education has been considered as a right which nations have an indisputable responsibility to guarantee their children (Abagi, 1998). The world conference on Education for All (EFA), held in Jomtien, Thailand in 1990 stipulated, among other goals, to ensure that by 2015, all children have access to and complete free and compulsory basic education (Sifuna, 1990). The initiative of the development of basic education is guided by the need for universal education (United Nations, 1990).

One of the important problems facing quality of basic education is the ineffectiveness. The ineffectiveness is reflected in the outcomes as measured by standardized tests, number of students promoted to the next grade after taking into account the background of students, their prior knowledge and the socio-economic status (Reynolds et al., 2000). According to United Nations (2021) ineffectiveness effects of schools, teachers and education in general has had significant negative effect on the improvement and performance of pupils. The output of basic education has been lower than expected, especially in more disadvantaged countries. Appavoo (2005) notes that poor school performance is seen as a "symptom" reflecting a larger underlying problem in the education system. According to the World Bank (2020), if the quality of education is undermined, schools do not provide the knowledge, skills and attitudes that a country needs in its citizens in order to boost development.

Since independence, Kenya has placed a considerable importance in the role of education in promoting economic and social development (Otiende & Sifuna, 1994). Basic education in Kenya begins the first phase of the formal educational system. The main purpose of basic education is to prepare children to participate fully in the social, political, and economic well-being of the country. The basic school curriculum, strategies and policies have therefore been designed to provide a functional and practical education that caters both to the needs of children who finish their education at the basic school level, and to those who wish to continue with secondary education. In 2003, Kenya introduced free and compulsory basic education. Under the subsidized basic education program, the government and development partners meet the cost of basic instructional materials and general purpose expenses.

However, for many years, results of the basic education in Kenya have been poor nationally. According to a study by Wanjiru (2020), since the introduction of the 8.4.4 system of education, performance in basic school national examinations has been unimpressive for all the years. This is

despite the introduction of subsidized basic education by the government in 2003, with the objective to allow all Kenyan children access education, ensure quality education by providing requisite resources to all schools equitably and thus allow for performance that is commensurate with the inputs therein. For instance, in primary schools, a study by the Kenya National Examinations Council (2021) reveals that majority of learners do not attain the minimum average 250 marks in the primary school national examinations.

Table 1: Sample primary school national average performance

Year	Average performance
2003	230
2008	231
2013	236
2018	235
2019	244
2020	232
2021	239

Source: Kenya National Examinations Council, 2021

2. Analysis of the Challenges in basic education in Kenya

2.1 System culture and development of effective strategies for grade improvement in Kenya

Studies show that there is a strong association between culture and effectiveness of the school education systems (Ali et al., 2016). High performing school education systems are linked with cultures that focus on concrete indicators and discrete indicators like beliefs, values, norms, vision and goals to be achieved by the education systems (Karadag et al., 2014). Positive education cultures are connected with improved student achievement, enhanced teacher collaboration and higher teacher self-determination (Yasin et al., 2017). The dimensions of education system culture, for example, professional development and learning partnership, have a significant relationship with student achievement (Hammond, 2018). Such cultures influence the beliefs, attitudes, and practices, shaping the school culture and the performance of the students (Dimmock et al., 2021). Ultimately, when there is a strong positive system culture, the student benefit since the staff work collaboratively to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning climate (Bhengu & Mthembu, 2014). Effective education system culture enables education stakeholders to share common values and traditions, and this impacts how they work and provide students with learning opportunities.

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However, this study found that in Kenya, the education system culture does not effectively support and challenge learners in the basic education. The system culture is based on strict formal processes and assessment-oriented procedures that have had negative impacts on the learners' performance in the basic education (Onyango, 2017). This has made education managers, including education officers and heads of the basic education not to seek out adequate opportunities to stretch the skills, goals, and strengths of students, teachers and parents alike. This is a display of non-commitment to a healthy, nurturing culture in the education system in Kenya. Findings also emerge that collaborative teamwork, recognition of individual and team efforts are weak in basic education systems. Moreover, the education system culture does not promote engagement from students and staff, as displayed by the limited sense of positivity and investment in the basic school institutions. For the educators who are equipped with the resources and skills to drive change within their schools, the limitation of the systems culture has been the biggest impediment in transforming school engagement processes. Furthermore, the culture of the basic education system does not adequately prepare for a life-long learning experiences.

Table 2: System culture and development of effective strategies for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

This study found that the education system culture for basic school:

- Does not provide effective communication within the stakeholder networks
- Does not cater for individual learners needs
- Does not enhance learners self-esteem
- Does not promote a school approach to assessment
- Does not provide a clear sense of purpose
- Have norms that reinforce inertia
- Does not clearly encourage collaboration

Source: Literature review, 2025

2.2 Operationalization of strategic management and leadership for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

The essential purpose of strategic leadership is to change the trajectory of the education sector. Strategic leaders anticipate, prepare and position education systems for the future (Serfontien & Hough, 2011). They create a vision, empower others and exercise flexibility, to create a strategic and viable future of the education system. Leaders who are strategic formulate the goals and strategies for increased performance of the education sector. By developing structures and processes that impact the present and future performances, operationalization of strategic leadership enables teams to work in sync, understand and embrace the vision and goals set ahead. Strategic leaders hold the power of influencing people to look at the bigger picture and work towards long-term education goals. As explained by Donmass (2009), Strategic leaders navigate through complex problems, influence employees and utilize opportunities that energizes the creation of more innovative education strategies.

In the basic education system in Kenya, this study found that there is insufficient utilization and operationalization of strategic leadership within the ranks of leadership hierarchy. According to Mulford (2003), this is characterized by the internal disputes and a lack of adequate support from members in the middle-management ranks (e.g. Principals, deputy principals and school department heads). The education leadership has structured educational relationships in ways that ignore effective learner-oriented focus, driving many teachers and students to a dead-end pessimistic view of their schooling. Many students drop out because they find themselves unable to take a positive role in the school setting that is largely incapable of responding effectively to their educational problems. Therefore, lack of strategic educational management has created wide gaps between intended educational goals and the resulting stark realities. The vast discrepancies between goal and outcome are essentially the result of widespread leadership and management failure.

Table 3: Operationalization of strategic management and leadership for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

This study found that the leadership and management of basic school:

- Do not identify strategic directions for grade improvement in basic education
- Lacks flexibility in implementation of education policies

- Do not consider the cost-effective approaches to implementation of the education strategies
- Do not embrace innovations, especially the use of learning technologies

Source: Literature review, 2025

2.3 Participative decision-making system for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

Participative decision making has been considered as a managerial tool to promote commitment aimed at improving performance of the education systems and schools. Participative decision contributes to the overall wellbeing of the educational institutions. It provides the opportunity for all the education stakeholders to provide input into the decision-making process related to school and learners performance. Therefore, there are reasons to believe that lack of opportunities for stakeholders to air their views or make inputs on work processes and issues that may hamper the realization of educational goals and objectives. Miller's (2016) review of employee participation noted that workers often have more complete knowledge of their work than managers. As a result, decisions made in conjunction with employees are made with a better pool of information. Also, employees who are involved in such decisions subsequently are better equipped to implement work procedures following the decision. According to Farooq (2021), participative decision making boosts employee morale because workers who are accorded recognition through participation perceive that management views them as intelligent, competent, and valued partners. This perception of being recognized and valued leads to employee satisfaction and subsequently greater productivity.

In Kenyan basic education system, studies indicate that there is limited employee involvement in decision making. Most of the decisions take the top-down approach and this has negatively affected employee commitment and the general productivity of the basic school education system. Lack of participation in decision making has robbed the employees the opportunity to develop skills and technical know-how required to achieve higher performance in the basic education. Teachers, for example, have lost morale and confidence and this has limited their creativity, commitment and job satisfaction in the place of work. In turn, this has created inefficiency and weak value-attachment to the teaching process. Moreover, due to the lack of participative decision making, school managers and teachers have to adhere to an internal logic that has remained virtually static and unchallenged in spite of significant change outside the educational sphere. Exclusion of stakeholders in decision making poses a challenge to the expectation of real long-term improvement in learning and grade improvement in the Kenyan basic education.

Table 4: Participative decision-making system for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

This study found that the decision making approach of basic school system:

- Does not consider participation as the answer and as the problem
- Does not effectively involve all the stakeholders
- Does not emphasize on knowledge, power and strategic sharing
- Does not embrace effective information networking
- Does not take into account the interest of all stakeholders

Source: Literature review, 2025

2.4 Extent of shared government vision or other expectations for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

Management with a shared vision can have a wide range of beneficial effects on the education system, including improving performance, promoting change, laying the groundwork for a strategic plan, motivating individuals and providing context for decisions. Shared vision helps in the implementation of many creative ideas in education sector that are never done due to lack of a common direction (Hoe, 2007). A shared vision results in an improvement in the quality of learning. It guides organizational learning and helps employees reach a common level of understanding. This fosters commitment and alignment with the organization's learning strategy. Shared vision leads to increase in the quality of learning. This engenders commitment and alignment with the learning direction taken by the organization (Husain et al., 2016). Managing through a common vision can improve performance, promote change, provide a framework for a

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strategic plan, motivate personnel, and provide a context for decisions. Shared vision as the embodiment of a group's collective goals and aspirations, as well as its shared sense of purpose and operating values. When team members share common or cooperative goals, they are more receptive to problem-solving approaches that enable them to learn from their mistakes. Without shared vision, are less likely to know what the organizational expectations and outcomes. In general, a shared vision can help motivate teams; promotes the sharing of perspectives and knowledge among members; fosters positive feelings and commitment among members; increases organizational engagement and legitimizes the acquisition and assessment of new knowledge.

In Kenya, this study found that the educational system for basic school does not pride effective vision sharing as an important foundation for proactive learning. This, in turn, limits energy, commitment and purpose among stakeholders especially the teachers. The education system does not clarify the system's direction on what to do and what to learn. This has made consistency in purpose and attainment of goals difficult within the education sector, especially for the teachers. Due to the ambiguous and uncertain environment within and outside the basic education systems, even if employees are motivated, it has been difficult to know what to learn without the shared vision. Without shared vision, managing through a maze of conflicting interests in the basic education systems has become more challenging and stressful. Moreover, while there exists some broad and specific outlines for strategy implementation, ineffectiveness in sharing vision has limited synergistic decision making in the basic education system. As many other studies have indicated, there is no need to run decisions up the chain of command because every employee, not just senior management, has a clear idea of the education system's strategic outcomes.

Table 5: Participative decision-making system for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

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Source: Literature review, 2025

2.5 Role of external circumstances on grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

The external factors like politics, economy, technology, environment and regulatory requirements are beyond our control and can make a huge impact on the education system's performance and success. The factors such as political stability, government policies, public investments, tax policies, local infrastructure, and national as well as international trade agreements affect implementation of education policies. The economic conditions like changes in the ratio of demand and supply may directly impact the school system's effectiveness and efficiency. Moreover, the economic factors including inflation, changes in the exchange rate, economic growth/decline and changes in interest rates has a direct impact on the performance of the education system. The technological factors such as impact of technological advancements and innovations, new equipment and technology awareness also have direct and indirect impacts on the education sector. Moreover, the environmental factors that majorly cover the environmental aspects that impact the education system's processes need to be evaluated. Furthermore, compliance and regulatory factors including the changes due to the compliance standards and their latest revisions can positively or negatively affect performance. The environment is the source of constraints, contingencies, problems as well as opportunities that affect school education systems.

In the Kenya, the education system for the basic education is not flexible to the changes outside the education system and in the external environment. Rigidity in dealing with unexpected environmental mutations means that the basic education system in Kenya is not able to perform effectively under the changing external circumstances. This is especially visible during times of political unrests where the schools are so much affected. Lack of effectiveness response to environmental circumstances has made the education sector affected by natural weather effects such as flooding. Since the external environment provides the education system with inputs,

which they transform to outputs through internal processes, it is important for basic education system in Kenya to be adaptable to the external changes. From a political perspective, disruptions have occurred in many schools when the government has not disbursed funds for the basic education. This has affected learning in most schools. In terms of technology, adoption of new equipment by the basic education does not match the new innovations in the other private and public sectors. Generally, the Kenya's education system for basic education must be aware of and fully understand the different manifestations of the external environment.

Table 6: Participative decision-making system for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

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- Does not take into account the interest of all stakeholders

Source: Literature review, 2025

2.6 Internal organizational school system circumstances and grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

McKinsey's conceptualization of internal organizational environment through the 7Ss framework posits that strategy, structure, skills, staff, systems, shared values and style, play a major role in influencing performance of all organizations both in public and private sectors. When searching for ways to improve an education system, the best place to start is from within. Internal improvements are an ongoing process, and each education system has its own specific needs. Changes in strategy and mission, organizational structure, operation management and innovation processes are often difficult to map out, but must be continually monitored to assess how well the system is meeting the mission and change strategies. This is the same for the roles, objectives, and responsibilities of individuals, departments and teams.

In Kenya, the basic education system has always worked towards improving the internal processes for better performance of the learners in both local and national examinations. However, this study found a few challenges. For instance, there is limited focus on local departments, procedures and target activities, which are often difficult to understand, leading to non-commitment to strategies aimed at achieving such activities. In some cases, there is poor communication from the top management, leading to more confusion about what is to be done by the implementation agencies at the local or school level. This has negatively affected the need to have a strong understanding of the education policies and strategies that are to be implemented. Although there are policies and work procedures to enable people get the right things done, some of the policies are not communicated effectively and often implementation using "crush activities". Moreover, the trainings put in place to enable people to perform essential work are not effective, as indicated by the little progress in the performance of the learners both in the internal and national examinations. Not all employees, especially the teachers, have not received the appropriate training that applies to their current duties and that is future-focused. In terms of extra learning materials, the system has not identified or developed cost effective materials which has made the extra learning too expensive for parents.

Table 7: Participative decision-making system for grade improvement in Kenya's basic education

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Source: Literature review, 2025

3. The Way Forward: Strategic Choices and Options

A strategic choice involves the process through which a decision is taken to choose a particular option from various alternatives. There can be various methods through which the final choice can be selected upon. In the context of education systems, some of the strategic choices make up a part of bigger strategic policies of the education institutions. Hence, important emphasis is given to decision makers to follow due diligence before coming up with a final strategic choice. On the other hand, strategic options are creative alternative action-oriented responses to the external situation that an education system faces. Strategic options take advantage of facts and actors, trends, opportunities and threat of the internal and external environment. Strategic options can be identified after an institutional assessment, keeping in mind the aspirations of an education system. The tool 'Strategic options' helps to identify and make a preliminary screening of alternative strategic options or perspectives.

3.1 Balanced Score Card approach

Balanced scorecard (BSC) refers to a strategic management performance metric used to identify and improve various internal business functions and their resulting external outcomes. It is a planning and management system that organizations use to: [1] communicate what they are trying to accomplish; [2] align the day-to-day work that everyone is doing with strategy; [3] prioritize projects, products, and services; [4] measure and monitor progress towards strategic targets. The balanced scorecard is a management system aimed at translating an organization's strategic goals into a set of organizational performance objectives that, in turn, are measured, monitored and changed if necessary to ensure that an organization's strategic goals are met. The BSC has four measurement perspectives. These can be summarized as follows: [1] Financial perspective: this is a strategy for growth, profitability, and risk from the perspective of the shareholder. [2] Customer perspective: this is a strategy for creating value and differentiation from the perspective of the customer. [3] Internal process perspective: the strategic priorities for various business processes create customer and shareholder satisfaction. [4] Learning and growth perspective: the priority from this perspective is to create a climate that supports organizational change, innovation, and growth.

The main benefits of balanced scorecards relate to the ease of assessing school performance across a variety of metrics, linking financial data to other indicators of school performance and monitoring progress towards measurable goals. In the Kenyan BASIC education, the balanced score card should be utilized to: [1] Generate transparency among all the education stakeholder groups [2] See clear patterns of performance amidst higher expectations [3] Engender confidence in the new school improvement practices [3] Eliminate redundancies in data collection and assessment, increase transparency, and facilitate improvement processes in the basic education [4] Coordinate resources to support the schools' efforts [5] Consolidate the unaligned parts of the improvement planning process into one continuous improvement structure that supported operational and strategic improvement in schools [5] Seamlessly connect aspects of performance: planning, measuring, monitoring, managing and communication. Using the balanced score card, the basic education system in Kenya should focus on the following strategic areas for the purpose of grade improvement.

Table 8: Balanced Score Card objectives

A. Customer perspective – including learners, staff, parents	
Objectives	Measures to be used
Learner/parents involvement	Percentage of enrolment out of highly valued program
Quality academic advising	Learner evaluation
Flexible course scheduling	Learner satisfaction survey
Quality instruction	Exam-passing rate
B. Internal business perspective: learner/stakeholder focus	
Objectives	Measures to be used
To achieve continuous improvement of services, facilities and resources to improve education service development	Service facilities to staff, New courses, syllabi, programs and curriculum changes
Quality assurance in basic school	Distribution of grades awarded, exit exam or learner

competency evaluation

Cost efficiency
Staff-to-learner ratio, Educational expenses per learner

C. Innovation and learning perspective: staff, and school system effectiveness

Objectives	Measures to be used
Staff motivation and development	Amount of budget spent on staff development; staff satisfaction index in staff survey; number of cross-trained or multi-skilled staff
Incorporating technology into teaching	Number of schools incorporating new technology Number of curriculum revisions in last five years;
Curriculum innovation	number of new learning methods introduced in last five years

D. Financial perspective

Objectives	Measures to be used
Maximize asset utilization	More efficient and effective use of educational facilities, services, systems and resources as measured by various usage studies and statistics

Source: Literature review, 2025

3.2 McKinsey's Strategic Horizons approach

The McKinsey Three Horizons of Growth model can help to prevent a gap between what an organization wants in the future and where it stands today. It gives organizations step-by-step insight into their growth and the achievement of their ultimate strategic goal. It is a strategic framework that helps to align the focus consistently between today's needs (Horizon 1), the future state of the company (Horizon 3), and the steps that lead to it (Horizon 2). Horizon 1 ideas provide continuous innovation to an organization's existing model and core capabilities in the short-term. Horizon 2 ideas extend an organization's existing model and core capabilities to new customers, markets, or targets. Horizon 3 is the creation of new capabilities to take advantage of or respond to disruptive opportunities or to counter disruption.

The three horizons framework offers a way to concurrently manage both current and future education opportunities for grade improvement in Kenya. The framework is especially important during this time when there are uncertainties about how to improve performance in the basic education. Using the McKinsey's Three Horizons, the basic education system in Kenya should focus on the following strategic objectives for the purpose of grade improvement.

Table 9: McKinsey's Strategic Horizons objectives

Objectives in Horizon 1	Measures to be used
Analysis of what is currently working, what may have peaked, what the strengths and weaknesses are, and what might be abandoned.	Learners performance in exams Portion of the resources funnelled into education. Service facilities to staff Staff-to-learner ratio
Objectives in Horizon 2	Measures to be used
Extending the basic school system to new opportunities.	New school enrolments basic graduation to secondary schools Acquired new resources for teaching and learning Added staff Explored innovations aimed at grade improvement
Objectives in Horizon 3	Measures to be used
Stabilizing grade improvement strategies, options and plans	National average performance National basic-to-secondary school transition

Source: Literature review, 2022

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3.3 PESTEL Strategic Approach

A PESTLE analysis studies the key external factors (Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental) that influence an organisation. It can be used in a range of different scenarios, and can guide people, professionals, staff and managers in strategic decision-making. In the Kenya's basic education, the PESTLE analysis is can be useful in providing prompts to the management and staff involved in the analysis of the changes in the school's environment that could affect current and future management decisions and school performance. Using the PESTEL strategic approach, the basic education system in Kenya should focus on the following measures for the purpose of grade improvement.

Table 10: PESTEL objectives

Political objectives	Measures to be used
Training services industry by government.	
Funding grants and initiatives	Quality performance in basic education
Increasing education subsidies	Number of registered learners
Mandatory employee benefits	Amount of resources in each school
Economic objectives	Measures to be used
Reducing cost of education	Amount of education subsidies
Infrastructure quality in Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cost of providing resources: ▪ Staff – teaching & support ▪ Basics – books/ paper ▪ Technology solutions
Government to reduce inflation	
Social objectives	Measures to be used
Integration with local community	Extent of public involvement in BASIC education policy decisions
Integration of students with special needs	Number of registered learners with special needs
Increasing parental preference	Parents' power in decision making

Technological	Measures to be used
Increasing technological impact on education	Number of learners using modern education innovations Learner satisfaction with new technologies
Environmental	Measures to be used
Adopting better school/classroom layout to ease teaching and learning	Number of structures with recommended layouts for teaching and learning
Ensuring proper waste disposal	
Increasing spaces for extracurricular and co-curricular activities	
Legal factors	Measures to be used
Introducing new legislations to reduce administrative burden of education processes	Number of education policies, plans, strategies and activities are being implemented
Staff compliance laws	Percentage of staff compliance

Source: Literature review, 2025

4. Evaluation matrix and priority Ranking and the strategic models

The study further utilized matrix evaluation and priority ranking of the strategic models for grade improvement in the basic schools in Kenya. The matrix evaluation and priority ranking was based on cost, efficiency, implementation period, complexity, sustainability, adaptability, relevance, effectiveness, impact, scope, size, failure risk and stakeholders' readiness. The purpose of the evaluation was to identify, the strategic option than can be best adapted for basic school system in Kenya.

Table 11: Evaluation matrix of the Strategic Options

Level 1 evaluation

Strategic Option	Cost	Efficiency	Implementation period	Complexity	Sustainability
Adapted Balanced Score Card	Less costly	Very efficient	Requires more time for implementation	Not very complex	Sustainable
Adapted McKinsey's Horizons	More costly	Efficient	Requires a lot of time	Complex	Less Sustainable
Adapted PESTEL	Less costly	Efficient	Does not accurately consider timeframe	Less complex	Less sustainable

Level 2 evaluation

Strategic Option	Adaptability	Relevance	Effectiveness	Impact	Scope
Adapted Balanced Score Card	Adaptable	Very Relevant	Very effective	Greatest impact	Nationwide
Adapted McKinsey's Horizons	Adaptable	Relevant	Effective	Great impact	Nationwide
Adapted PESTEL	Less adaptable	Relevant	Effective	Great impact	Nationwide

Level 3 evaluation

Strategic Option	Size	Failure Risk	Stakeholders' readiness	Customer focus	Internal consistency
Adapted Balanced Score Card	Large	Low risk	Stakeholders are ready for the strategy	Learner-oriented	Considers consistency
Adapted McKinsey's Horizons	Large	High risk	Stakeholders are ready for the strategy	Learner-oriented	Considers consistency
Adapted PESTEL	Large	High risk	Stakeholders are ready for the strategy	Public-oriented	Focuses on external environment

Source: Literature review, 2025

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Table 12: Priority ranking of Adapted Balanced Score Card

Strategic area	Finding	Better than other models?
Cost	Less costly	Yes
Efficiency	Very efficient	Yes
Implementation period	Less implementation period	Yes
Complexity	Less complex	Yes
Sustainability	Very sustainable	Yes
Adaptability	Very adaptable	Yes
Relevance	Very relevant	Yes
Effectiveness	Very effective	Yes
Impact	Greatest impact	Yes
Scope	Nationwide	Similar to the other models
Size	Large	Similar to the other models
Failure risk	Low risk	Yes
Stakeholders' readiness	Stakeholders are ready for the strategy	Similar to the other models
Customer focus	Learner-centred	Yes
Internal consistency	Considers internal consistency	Yes

Source: Literature review, 2025

5. Conclusion

Analysis of the three models revealed that the Adapted Balanced Score Card strategic approach that can be best adapted for improvement of grade performance in the Kenya's basic schools.

6. Recommendation

This study found that of the three strategic choices (Adapted Balanced Score Card, McKinsey's Strategic Horizons, PESTEL Strategic), the Adapted Balanced Score Card ranks higher than the other two strategic models. The study therefore recommends the use of Adapted Balanced Score Card for improving the performance of basic education in Kenya. The model is recommended because it was found to be the most effective in improving strategy communication and execution; alignment of projects and initiatives; management of information; alignment of organization and studying of learner's performance. However, it is worth to note that this study was limited to Adapted Balanced Score Card, McKinsey's Strategic Horizons and PESTEL Strategic choices. The future studies should explore the applicability of the other strategic models in the context of basic education in Kenya and other developing countries.

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